

LEARNING ENGLISH IN THE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATIONAL SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article will talk about independent learning, which is one of the best ways to raise the creative potential of students studying in the specialty English in higher education institutions. This article will consider as an example the problems that exist in this direction today and a number of proposals for creating new ways of organizing independent education and a number of methodological experiments carried out for this purpose, and the methods that can be applied in practice will be covered in detail.

Key words: Independent Education, independent thinking, active participant-reflector, topics of Independent Education.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ПРИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ У СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. в этой статье пойдет речь о самостоятельном обучении, которое является одним из лучших способов повысить творческий потенциал студентов, обучающихся по специальности английский язык в высших учебных заведениях. В этой статье в качестве примера будут рассмотрены проблемы, существующие сегодня в этом направлении, а также ряд предложений по созданию новых способов организации самостоятельного обучения и ряд методических экспериментов, проведенных с этой целью, и будут подробно рассмотрены методы, которые могут быть применены на практике.

Ключевые слова: независимое образование, независимое мышление, активный участник-рефлектор, темы независимого образования.

In today's educational institutions, in teaching using modern pedagogical Technologies, wide opportunities have been created for teaching foreign languages using advanced methods in the process of Independent Education, for training professionals who can speak these languages fluently. The application of international standards in the teaching of foreign languages in the world, modernization of the content of teaching, private issues of the use of modern technologies in professional education, further exacerbated the need for the use of advanced foreign experience in the development of professional competencies of the teacher. In Europe, it is important to carry out scientific research on the development of professional competencies in foreign languages, the integration of competencies, the formation of harmony among standard requirements and training programs, the Coordination of developed criteria for strategies used in the study of other foreign languages.

In independent education, student activity assumes the development of linguistic competencies of future Foreign Language teachers, the analysis of language learning and language

acquisition, linguistic competencies of students in the educational process, as well as the traditional teaching system and modern teaching technologies. The fact that the formation and development of linguistic competencies of students in English lessons is closely related to the ability to correctly choose methods and methods of Education assumes an increased interest in acquiring foreign languages and the correct Organization of Independent Education in language learning.

While the tasks performed by students in independent education are not very successful, the teacher cannot criticize them. And the teacher is the supervisor during the process. On the contrary, it is necessary that the creative thinking of students is encouraged. The lesson ends with the stimulation of quickly given answers, their replenishment, assessment of students. The Q & A (Discussion) method allows you to pass distance lessons more meaningfully and fun. The student should be able to freely say his opinion, not afraid to make mistakes. Such an environment should be formed in the lesson. The tasks of the student in the technology of training through a question answer are as follows:

1. Thinking of expected answers and objections.

2. The importance of believing in one's own knowledge is that there will be an opportunity to observe students from the teacher at a time when they are operating freely. As a result, it is possible to learn more about student activity, fantasies, creative abilities, workaholics, behavior in independent education. Teaching students with interest in teaching English and achieving complete mastery of knowledge is one of the main goals of modern pedagogical technologies.

Another method of teaching English is the modern interactive method. According to the content of the method, a new grammatical topic is published in the lesson, and the teacher must explain it in different ways, that is, draw different drawings on the Board, show them with movements, compare them with the previously mentioned topic, involve students in thinking with reinforcing questions. In phonetic practice, however, short conversations in a mostly audio text are listened to and, in a calm state, the text on paper, whose words are dropped, exactly corresponding to the conversation in this audio text, is filled and matured to the teacher through the internet. With the text given to the student, the conversation in the audio text will be the same. The student can successfully fulfill the condition only when the text is listened to independently with extreme elegance and keeps new phrases in mind. In this, through listening and understanding, oral speech, skills and qualifications are formed. Listening and understanding is closely related to the reading process.

Independent education is one of the forms of education aimed at the skills and competencies that must be formed in the student and knowledge that must be acquired by the student from a specific subject in the curriculum, and is carried out mainly outside the audience on the basis of teacher advice and recommendations. Independent education of the student is organized under the guidance of the teacher to master the course work, course project, thesis to conferences, preparation of articles and, without the guidance of the teacher, basically, the specified part of a particular course independently read by the student himself.

The main objectives of the Independent Education of students are:
the fact that the student has the skills to master new knowledge in a thorough independent way;

- having the skills to be able to track down the necessary information, identify convenient

ways and means of learning;

- effective use of information sources and addresses;
- work with educational and scientific literature, regulatory documents;
- work with e-learning literature and data bank;
- effective use of the internet network;
- database analysis;
- defines a rational solution of given assignments;
- systematic and creative approach to completing tasks;

In the context of today's globalization, it is advisable to use advanced pedagogical technologies and active methods in the educational process, to implement the newly produced technical means, to encourage more students to work independently, to widely use different ways of teaching lessons from advanced experiments. Another aspect is important that in the system of higher education, it is necessary to ensure the effective organization of the training of special subjects so that those who receive education have a tendency to their chosen profession, develop their abilities, knowledge and skills, and form as specialists in their chosen areas.

In the process of successful independent education, the role of the teacher, as a cognitive specialist, goes to the role of a coach, which helps students master the strategies necessary for learning. The main type of activity is to help the teacher create his own ideas about the educational goals for students.

The concept of Independent Education is often associated with other approaches to education, such as personalization and student-oriented education. Discussion of self-education often occurs in the context of important issues such as the role and relationship between the student and the teacher, as well as the role of ICT in the learning process.

In conclusion, the methodology for the formation of learning English through basic competencies in the process of Independent Education in students, the use of pedagogical technologies in the process of independent learning, provides practical assistance to students to develop verbal speech, listening comprehension, writing, reading skills and communicate freely.

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